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D7.6: REPORT ON ENGAGEMENT WITH USER COMMUNITIES AND ON USER RESEARCH NEEDS

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Abstract

This Deliverable, D7.6, is part of Work Package 7 “Training and Engagement” which aims to expand the service portfolio and widen service coverage for new user communities. The new user communities include the fields of social sciences and humanities; built heritage; palaeontology and palaeoanthropology; and archaeology. These are widely varying and disparate groups, with different types of internal organisation and different degrees of coordination as well as different levels of engagement with scientific research. Here, we propose a plan for engagement with new communities. Some strategies are common to the four new user communities. This maximises effectiveness and impact and minimises duplication. It will also allow us to easily extend our strategy to any further future new user groups. However, we recognise that the differences between the groups mean that we will need flexible strategies that take into account these dissimilarities. In all cases, we recognise the importance of two-way dialogue to seek the opinions of members of the user groups and the need to adjust IPERION HS’s offering to take account of the needs of the different groups.

We propose to monitor the engagement of members of the different groups as they request Trans-National Access and calculate Key Performance Indicators that will allow us to monitor the engagement of new user communities compared to more established users.

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Abbreviations

Words or Phrase	Abbreviation
Centro Nacional de Investigación sobre la Evolución Humana	CENIEH
Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas	CSIC
Universita ta Malta	UOM
Stiftung Preussischer Kulturbesitz	SPK
University College London	UCL
Historic Buildings and Monuments Commission for England	HEL
Cultural Heritage	CH
Earth Sciences	ES
Environmental Sciences	EnvS
Electro Spin Resonance	ESR
European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science	E-RIHS
European Union	EU
Heritage Science	HS
Human Evolution	HE
Million years	Ma
Natural Heritage	NH
Optically Stimulated Luminescence	OSL
Physical Heritage	PH
Preparatory Phase	PP
Quality Assurance	QA
Quality Control	QC
Radiocarbon	¹⁴ C
Terrestrial Cosmogenic Nuclides	TCN
Universal Chronology Service	UCS
Work Package	WP
Palaeoanthropology and Palaeontology Community	PPC

Narrative (technical) description

This Deliverable D7.6 is part of IPERION HS Work Package 7 (Training and Engagement).

WP 7 aims to engage with users throughout their journey through IPERION HS. For successful trans-national access provision, it is essential that this engagement is intensive. By our estimation, there are several 10.000 potential users in the EU alone (estimation based on the number of academically active researchers in heritage science, which we see as an umbrella term for conservation science, buildings research and archaeological science), and this WP has developed an intensive plan for engagement activities distributed in individual tasks as follows:

- Pre-access, engagement of four types of specific communities where there is a prescient need to develop an understanding of what access IPERION HS can provide and what the added value of engagement with IPERION HS is:

(i) social sciences and humanities; (ii) built environment; (iii) paleontology and paleoanthropology; (iv) archaeology.

- Throughout, and once the interest in engagement is developed, there is usually a need for training, which could either be in the practical skill of proposal development, or it could be in the development of a deeper understanding of the potential of a particular research facility – this could be either pre-access or post-access training, as well as training during access, which is when most hands-on training takes place.

- Post-access, we will develop a structure (User Forum) to engage with users in an organized way, both to enable them to share experience and skills, but also to enable them to form an independent voice and thus feedback into the management structures of IPERION HS. This will include User Forum conferences and meetings and form an invaluable feedback loop for the project and will ultimately increase the quality of access provision.

The WP will work in close alignment with WPs 2-4, where user helpdesks will be organized to deal with access- and platform-specific enquiries, and with WP8, representing the unique access point to the training activities and through which communication and dissemination of user-led research will be enabled.

1.1 Deliverables and Milestones

In the third reporting period of IPERION HS, there were scheduled deliverables.

Deliverables 7.1, 7.2 and 7.3 and MS06 were all completed and submitted on time during the first reporting period, and the next deadlines are D7.4 in 30.09.2023, D7.5 in 30.11.2023 and D7.6 in 29.02.2024.

Activity did continue as part of the tasks, as described below.

D7.6 encompasses the tasks 7.3, 7.4 , 7.5 and 7.6

1.2 T7.3 Engagement with the social sciences and humanities community

Task leader: UOM

1.2.1 Description of the T7.3

The communities of curators, conservators, heritage managers, paleographers, codicologists, art historians, historians, social scientists and other heritage scholars are in some ways well engaged by the heritage science community, however, there is a continuous need to strongly engage specifically with this layer of our potential user community. On the one hand, this is because of the specific skills and expertise that can be brought on board (e.g. in conservation), but on the other hand, this is because of the lack of scientific training that may result in a lack of understanding of the potential of scientific research that can be enabled by IPERION HS. There is therefore a need to feed into training activities for the access providers as well as for the users, as well as a pressing need to disseminate the information about IPERION HS in professional bodies such as the International Institute of Conservation, the International Council of Museums – Committee for Conservation and other relevant bodies. We will promote jointly organized sessions at their events and conferences, and thus promote a better understanding of the IPERION HS capacity and community. The task will result in a report on social sciences and humanities community research needs that could be addressed using heritage science research facilities (D7.6).

1.2.2 Explanation of the work carried out per T7.3

The summary of the organisations within the Social Sciences and Humanities that have been contacted through various media from 2019 to date are:

A combination of conservation, conservation science and museum organisations as follows:

- European: ENCORE, NEMO, ECCO, ICON (UK), IfM/SPK (Germany)
- International: IIC, ICOMOS ISCS, ICOM CC
- US and Canada: AIC, GCI, CCI

1.2.3 Methodology used

The outreach methodology used was as follows whenever possible:

- STEP 1: Identify National Key Experts in the Identified Fields
- STEP 2: Start a Dialogue
- STEP 3: Compile a Report on the Key Areas/Questions to 'Answer'
- STEP 4: Decide via which Media/Method to Transfer the Information (based on Step 3)

The outreach methodology used for each organisation is given in the table below:

Name	Abbreviation	Method of Outreach
American Institute for Conservation	AIC	Online post on the AIC Global Conservation forum
International Institute for Conservation	IIC	An article on IPERION HS was accepted and appeared online on NiC Issue 90 June/July 2022 under " <i>News in Brief</i> "
Getty Conservation Institute	GCI	Online meeting held with Head of Science and an article was prepared for the GCI online bulletin
European Network for Conservation-Restoration Education	ENCORE	Online discussion with President of ENCORE
Network of European Museum Organisations	NEMO	Several informal discussions held, short description of IPERION HS posted on NEMO social media
Institute for Museum Research and Prussian Cultural Heritage Foundation Canadian Conservation Institute	IfM CCI	An online discussion was coordinated by SPK and held with the director and deputy director for IfM; webinar links sent for viewing An online meeting was held with the director of research, conservation and scientific services. An article reviewed by Jana Striova and Laura Benassi from the coordination office was sent to be distributed by the CCI communications team.

<p>The Institute of Conservation (UK)</p> <p>European Confederation of Conservator-Restorers' Organisations</p>	<p>ICON</p> <p>ECCO</p>	<p>An article about IPERION HS was posted on the ICON website after several online discussions</p> <p>Following an introduction to IPERION HS at the ECCO board meeting and the participation of ECCO vice-president in the IPERION HS webinar dedicated to the SSH communities at the end of 2021, a follow up email with an introductory presentation on IPERION HS was sent to the board and it was confirmed that it was sent to the ECCO mailing list on 29/03/2022</p>
<p>ICOMOS ISCS (International Scientific Committee on Stone)</p>	<p>ISCS</p>	<p>A short write-up for the next ISCS online newsletter was sent and accepted</p>

Table 1 Institutions that were addressed within T7.4 (Built Environment Community)

1.2.4 Other activities

1.2.4.1 ECCO Committee Presentation

TransNational Access across Europe

ARCHLAB

- ARCHIVES -
Access to specialised knowledge and organized scientific information dataset largely unpublished from prestigious archives

FIXLAB

- FIXED LABORATORIES -
Access to large-scale and medium-scale facilities for sophisticated investigations on samples and whole objects

MOLAB

- MOBILE LABORATORIES -
Access to advanced mobile analytical instrumentation for non-invasive measurements on movable or immovable art objects

How to Access:

- Researchers, conservators, professionals can submit a proposal through the IPERION HS website.
- There are two evaluation cut-off deadlines per year. Your proposal will be evaluated by an independent international Peer Review Panel. If it will be approved, you can access the IPERION HS facilities.
- userhelpdesk@iperionhs.eu

www.iperionhs.eu

Fig. 1 Presentation of the TNA activities at ECCO Committee

Fig. 2 Examples of TNA activities presented at ECCO (2020)

On November 19th, 2020, UM attended the ECCO committee meeting to give a presentation on IPERION HS and its transnational access. Elis Marçal, ECCO president and Sebastian Dobruskin, vice-president at the time, as well as another 10 members of the committee were present for the call and a Q&A session was held after. Following this session, committee member Stefan Belinshki participated in the HS Academy webinar dedicated to the SSH communities and an information presentation was sent out to all members of the ECCO by email.

1.2.4.2 ICON Paper conference

Fig. 3 Heading of the ICON Paper conference (2021)

In May 2021, JoAnn Cassar together with Matija Strlic presented a paper on *The Opportunities of a Global, Shared Research Infrastructure for the Conservation Community* at the 19th Triennial Conference of ICOM-CC (International Council of Museums - International Committee for

Conservation). The audience of approximately 500 people later participated in a Q&A session wherein interesting questions related to transnational access were asked to the speakers.

A video recording of the presentation is available on following websites: e-rihs.eu, Heritage Malta, and on the webpage of the Department of Conservation and Built Heritage, University of Malta.

<https://www.icom-cc2021.org/programMonday.aspx>

The paper was published and is available on the IPERION HS website: http://www.iperionhs.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/08/1601_385_CASSAR_STRLIC_Paper.pdf

1.2.4.3 #HSAcademy Webinar on Arts and Humanities

Fig. 4 Promotional materials of the Arts and Humanities webinar

LINK: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=YHjG9yTZub4>

The sixth webinar in the #HSAcademy series was guest-moderated by JoAnn Cassar (University of Malta) in October 2021 with the aim to explore the potential of IPERION HS facilities to address research needs posed by humanities and social science scholars. The webinar was structured in a way wherein members from two areas within the SSH communities presented realtime research

queries whilst members from the IPERION HS platforms responded on the potential ways on how this initiative can help.

Stefan Belishki (Curator, National Academy of Arts, Sofia) explored research questions related to paintings by Ivan Mrkvička and how their palette and possibly authenticity could be explored using IPERION HS facilities and Joan Abela (Archivist, University of Malta) discussed a collection of sealed letters and research questions related to how the material evidence could be analysed and how the letters could be read without opening.

The webinar answered to the questions arising from the Arts and Humanities community in relations with a better knowledge, interpretation, authentication, preservation and restoration of heritage.

1.2.5 Achievements

A participant satisfaction survey held after the HS Academy webinar indicated that an international audience of 143 participants listened in with 97% of them indicating a satisfaction level above average. The attendees were from varied communities including archaeology, built environment, social sciences and humanities, conservation science, heritage science and chemistry. Below are the results of this survey:

Webinar #06

Webinar #06

Q2 Please rate your overall satisfaction with this webinar (1 being poor-10 being excellent)

Fig. 5 Survey related to the Arts and Humanities webinar

Thanks to dialogues held with all local entities from the SSH communities throughout the IPERION HS project, the core through which the present National Node for the upcoming E-RIHS was formed. To date, all 8 local entities in cultural heritage form part of the Steering Committee and seven meetings have been held. As a node, the work done includes: feedback to the National Research Strategy and National Education Strategy, collaboration with NARCH (National Research Agenda for Cultural Heritage) and an upcoming local training school on multidisciplinary in heritage with an Archaeological theme.

The E-RIHS.mt website has also been launched since 2023 reporting national and international news in the cultural heritage community.

Fig. 6 E-RIHS mt website

1.3 T7.4 Engagement with the built environment community

Task Leader: SPK / Fraunhofer

1.3.1 Description of the Task T7.4

The heritage-built environment represents a significant new community for the IPERION HS project and significant engagement will be necessary in order to develop a user base of building surveyors, facility managers, building managers, construction engineers, building conservators and building physicists, but also climate scientists. IPERION HS will be offering several access services to this community, and we will need to be able to present the added value of cross-disciplinary research performed through the three platforms. This will be achieved through intensive engagement of international bodies and associations such as ICOMOS - International Council on Monuments and Sites, but also through the more specific communities of BIM – building information modelling specialists etc. Joint events as well as organization of joint sessions at annual or biennial conferences of these associations will be carried out in order to develop fruitful collaboration. T7.4 lead is responsible for D7.2. The task will result in a report on built environment community research needs that could be addressed using heritage science research facilities (D7.6)

1.3.2 Explanation of the work carried out per T7.4.

1.3.2.1 Characteristics of the communities

The built heritage community is very fragmented comprising many different disciplines from architects, craft companies, conservators/restorers in public and private institutions. Conservators or restorers with a university background may know certain analytical methods but may not be aware of IPERION HS.

Especially craftspeople will be interested in learning more about new analytical tools in order to assess and understand better historic and traditional technologies and to better tailor conservation measures. Often more in-depth information is needed and knowledge about the new high-tech instrumentation for analytics is missing and not well understood. Here support is needed to reach this target group.

1.3.2.2 General needs

Communication must be enhanced to better inform the built heritage sector about what IPERION can offer.

Training and education workshops in the new analytical methods should enhance necessary skills and can contribute to achieve a more sustainable renovation/restoration/preservation of built heritage.

“Translators” can facilitate access for craftsmen helping them with formulating suitable questions and selecting the appropriate methods to find solutions, and hopefully co-create new research questions and projects.

1.3.2.3 Strategies for engagement

- STEP 1: Identify National and International Key Experts in the target areas who can then facilitate contact with Key players in the various organisations we wish to engage with.
- STEP 2: Engage with the identified Key players and Start a Dialogue - small groups consisting of the IPERION team with key experts and their international contacts.
- STEP 3: Identify the Key Areas/Questions to 'Answer' – using the information from STEP 2, identify the ways in which we can target the audience based on the help they require and/or the queries they have.

Bundesanstalt für Materialprüfung (Federal Institute for Materials Testing (D))	BAM	https://www.bam.de/Navigation/EN/Home/home.html
British Institute of Non-Destructive Testing (UK)	BINDT	https://www.bindt.org
Building Research Establishment (UK)	BRE	https://www.bregroup.com/
Climate Heritage Network	CHN	https://climateheritage.org/
International Committee for Documentation of Cultural Heritage	CIPA	https://www.cipaheritagedocumentation.org/
Deutsche Gesellschaft für Zerstörungsfreie Prüfung (D)	DGZfP	https://www.dgzfp.de
Deutsches Nationalkomitee für Denkmalschutz	DNK	http://www.dnk.de/
ECTP - Heritage and Regeneration	ECTP	http://www.ectp.org
European Confederation of Conservator-Restorers' Organisations	ECCO	http://www.ecco-eu.org
European Federation for Construction Chemicals	EFCC	http://www.efcc.eu/
European Federation for Non-Destructive Testing	EFNDT	http://www.efndt.org
European Federation of Natural Stone Industries	EUROROC	www.euroroc.net
European Mineralogical Union	EMU	http://eurominunion.org
Getty Conservation Institute	GCI	https://www.getty.edu/conservation
International Institute for Conservation	IIC	https://www.iiconservation.org
International Council on Monuments and Sites	ICOMOS	https://www.icomos.org/en
International Centre for the Study of the Preservation and Restoration of Cultural Property	ICCROM	https://www.iccrom.org
Sustainable Traditional Buildings Alliance	STBA	https://stbauk.org/home
Verband der Restauratoren Union of Restorers (D)	VDR	https://www.restauratoren.de

International Association for Science and Technology of Building Maintenance and Monuments Preservation WTA	WTA	https://www.wta-international.org/en/
Zentralverband des Handwerks / German Federation of Skilled Crafts	ZDH	https://www.zdh.de/en/

Table 2 Institutions that were addressed within T7.4 (Built Environment Community)

1.3.2.4 Achievements

IPERION HS Webinar series: Webinar 5: IPERION HS Built Environment Research Services (14.09.2021)

[#HSAcademy webinar 5/2021: Built Heritage - YouTube](#)

Organizer: Ralf Kilian (Fraunhofer)

Moderators: Matija Strlič (ZKVD, Slovenia), Ralf Kilian (Fraunhofer, Germany)

Invited speakers:

- Costanza Miliani – National Research Council CNR, Institute of Heritage Science, IT “MOLAB - On-site non-invasive diagnostics and monitoring of historical build heritage”
- John Hughes – University of the West of Scotland “The effects of fire on building stone at the Mackintosh Building, Glasgow School of Art, Scotland”
- Josep Grau Bove – UCL, UK “Modelling the 5 layers of data in historic buildings”
- Jan van ’t Hof – Cultural Heritage Agency of the Netherlands, NL “Building(s) for the future”

Fig. 7 Promotional advertisement of the webinar on Built Heritage

The webinar discusses the role of Heritage Science in the preservation, restoration and understanding of historic buildings and monuments and describes the on-site non-invasive diagnostics and monitoring services available in IPERION HS.

Fig. 8 Screenshot of the webinar

Fig. 9 Disciplinary engagement analysis following Webinar #5 on built environment research facilities (above left) and satisfaction rating (1-lowest; 10-highest satisfaction) (above right) and the geographical outreach (bottom).

1.3.2.5 Outreach

1. **The 4th International Conference on Energy Efficiency in Historic Buildings** - October 5-8 2020 – Benediktbeuern, Germany
2. **9th ECTP Conference** – December 2-3 2021 – Madrid, Spain
Introduction of the IPERION HS services to the European Construction Technology Platform by Paula Carmona (Instituto de Química Física Rocasolano CSIC).
3. **Byggnadsvårdens convention** – September 21-23 2022 – Mariestad, Sweden
Presentation of IPERION HS to the built heritage community in Sweden by Marei Hacke (Swedish National Heritage Board).

1.4 T7.5 Engagement with the palaeoanthropology and palaeontology community

Task Leader Cenieh

1.4.1 7.1 Description of the Task T7.5

The paleoanthropology community represents yet another new community of users for which IPERION HS will represent an attractive offer of scientific facilities. However, there has not been sustained and promoted collaboration in this field in the past, specifically with communities of anthropology, paleontology, DNA studies, dating and taphonomic studies related to the study of human biological and cultural evolution. This research area is rapidly expanding, specifically with the development of ever better and more accurate techniques to study DNA of past populations and other proteomic and morphological evidence. The IPERION HS project will offer new access services specifically for these communities and targeted engagement will be necessary e.g. with ESHE - European Society for the study of Human Evolution, or The Paleontological Association in order to develop joint events and shared conference sessions or presentations. The task will result in a report on paleoanthropology and paleontology community research needs that could be addressed using heritage science research facilities (D7.6). **T7.5 lead is responsible for D7.6.**

1.4.2 7.2 Explanation of the work carried out per T7.5

Abbreviations

Words or Phrase	Abbreviation
<i>Centro Nacional de Investigación sobre la Evolución Humana</i>	CENIEH
Cultural Heritage	CH
Earth Sciences	ES
Environmental Sciences	EnvS
Electro Spin Resonance	ESR
European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science	E-RIHS
European Union	EU
Heritage Science	HS
Human Evolution	HE
Million years	Ma

Natural Heritage	NH
Optically Stimulated Luminescence	OSL
Physical Heritage	PH
Preparatory Phase	PP
Quality Assurance	QA
Quality Control	QC
Radiocarbon	¹⁴ C
Terrestrial Cosmogenic Nuclides	TCN
Universal Chronology Service	UCS
Work Package	WP
Palaeoanthropology and Palaeontology Community	PPC

1.4.3 Task 7.5 Background & Highlights

This study aims to understand the real needs of the PPC community and is based mainly on the results of a survey addressed to various types of institutions within the community (research, academic, laboratories...) Within the framework of this subtask 7.5 .6, an initial inventory of 44 possible dating methods applicable to most HS materials and their associated (geo) chronology laboratories within the EU has been carried out. Only 8 of these dating methods, divided into 3 separate categories, were selected for the core of the UCS survey.

The online survey, designed as 2 separate yet complementary questionnaires targeting general and detailed aspects of laboratory strategies and processes, was open for responses from January 8th 2024 until February 20th 2024, with a total of 140 questionnaires, encompassing 13 EU countries, received from 305 contacted experts/laboratories/institutions.

Most of the institutions surveyed either knew about Palaeontology or were already involved in the field. Interestingly, most samples dated are associated to the PPC fields as opposed to CS. Nonetheless, all laboratories surveyed are open to date/characterise new materials or venture into new HS applications.

The general consensus from this survey is that the IPERION HS initiative is welcomed and encouraged, however, several aspects related to the type of access, funding and sample time capacity/technology are still questionable and require further investigation, even with practical days.

In addition to this survey, several webinars, conferences and other similar events have been carried out, mainly ON-LINE to facilitate access to them for the largest possible number of users, and aimed mainly at the paleontological community, in order to show the great potential that IPERION HS offers to its members and promote collaboration with this community.

Task 7.5 of IPERION HS was conceived as a study to find out the resource needs of the PPC to which the IPERION network can respond, which includes, among others, all the most relevant techniques used to date heritage. Some dating methods used in IPERION HS may be better known than others, since they are more widely or routinely used in more studied scientific disciplines, such as Geosciences, Archaeology and Conservation-Preservation Sciences, compared to others that they are limited to a more exclusive area and for which the resources offered by IPERION HS can be very useful.

IPERION HS's variety of disciplines, such as material culture science and art technology research. As such, 14C, dendrochronology and luminescence are examples of dating methods widely used in early fields, unlike chromatography, patination or seriation, which are not as well-known and can be of great use to PPC.

The main objective of d is to create a "one door knock" service that helps PPC users to choose the most appropriate dating technique, laboratory and sampling method for their sample needs. Users can be from museums, government, academic and research organizations related to palaeontologists and paleoanthropologists. In turn, the expert service provided by IPERION HS must be a combination of key provisions, strategic sampling, most appropriate dating method, expert advice, forgery analysis and accurate dating.

1.4.3.1 Age Range & Overlap

The age range of IPERION HS is still not defined and is still debatable. If HS covers Tangible CH, Intangible CH, Underwater CH and NH, but now involves the Palaeontology and Palaeoanthropology communities, the age range has to cover the Anthropocene, Holocene and Pleistocene, i.e., at least the past 8-10 Ma to cover all HE and History, from modern to pre-historic times.

1.4.3.2 Research Resources

Within the framework of this task 7.5, an initial inventory of the different research resources, means and techniques that IPERIOS offers has been compiled, and many of them would be useful for research and work carried out in the field of the paleontology.

The inventory of facilities and experts encompasses its shows in the following information:

ARCHLAB

Access to physical and digital (offline) data collections in European museums or conservation institutes, such as objects, technical images, samples and reference materials, analytical data and conservation documentation, in datasets largely unpublished from ten large archives of prestigious European museums, galleries and research institutions.

The following list shows the different Digital & Physical Archives that can be accessed:

- The British Museum (UK)
- Prussian Cultural Heritage Foundation (SPK)
- The National Gallery (UK)
- Royal Museums of Art and History (BE)
- Spanish Cultural Heritage Institute (ES)
- National Institute of Heritage (RO)
- Research Laboratory for Historical Monuments (FR)
- Groningen Institute of Archaeology (NL)
- Center for Research and Restoration of the Museums of France (FR):
- Royal Institute for Cultural Heritage (BE)
- Historic England, Heritage Science (UK)
- The Craft Laboratory (SE)
- Cultural Heritage Agency (NL)
- Opificio delle Pietre Dure (IT)

FIXLAB

The unique FIXLAB services offered to the CH community embrace:

- advanced state-of-the-art instrumentation
- dedicated facilities with teams of experts in the field of micro-analysis of CH artefacts
- novel developments resulting from IPERION HS joint research activities to progressively improve access
- development of both new sample-positioning devices at a micro-scale and software tools for the integration of imaging data

There are at least 107 dating methods that could be used in the multiple disciplines involving HS. Such methods go from precise numerical dating to relative-associative-evaluative approaches, and also involving incremental dating techniques. These dating methods are common to the various HS disciplines and other sciences such as Geology, Geochronology, **Paleontology and Paleoanthropology.**

The following list shows the different laboratories and different techniques that can be accessed:

FACILITIES

IT - National Institute for Nuclear Physics - INFN CHNET

IT - National Institute for Nuclear Physics - INFN LNGS

CZ - Czech Academy of Sciences - ITAM
DE - Curt-Engelhorn-Centre Archaeometry gGmbH - CEZA
DE - Heinz Maier Leibniz Zentrum, MLZ
ES - Spanish National Research Council - CSIC
ES - National Research Centre on Human Evolution - CENIEH
FR - Grand Louvre Accelerator for Elemental Analysis - AGLAE
FR - AST RX PLATFORM
FR - Synchrotron SOLEIL - SOLEIL
FR - National Centre for Scientific Research, IPANEMA
FR - Heritage Science Molecular Omics Platform - HS OMICS
GR - Foundation for Research and Technology- Hellas - FORTH IESL
HU - Institute for Nuclear Research - ATOMKI
HU - Budapest Neutron Center - BNC
NL - Vrije University in Amsterdam - VU GGL
PT - National Laboratory for Civil Engineering - LNEC
SE - Swedish National Heritage Board - RAA
SE - SciLifeLab
SI - The Institute for the Protection of Cultural Heritage of Slovenia - IPCHS
UK - English Heritage, Fort Cumberland - HE FC
UK - University College of London - UCL
UK - University of York, BioArCh
FIXLAB - Providers (23)

TECHNIQUES

Biological analysis

- Enzyme-Linked ImmunoSorbent Assays (ELISA)
- Ancient DNA analysis (aDNA)
- Immunofluorescence microscopy (IFM)

Conservation techniques and preparation methods

- Laser cleaning
- Freeze Drying
- Skeleton preparation

Dating

- Accelerator Mass Spectrometry (AMS) - Radiocarbon dating
- Optically Stimulated Luminescence (OSL)
- Electron Spin Resonance (ESR)
- Uranium Series
- Paleomagnetism
- Zooarchaeology
- Archeobotany

Environmental parameters measurements

- Air Exchange Rate and Ventilation (AER)
- Pollutant Monitoring

- Environmental simulation

Imaging (multiscale and multispectral)

- Mid infrared hyperspectral imaging (MIRHSI)
- Multi spectral luminescence microscope (MSLM)
- Combined micro-XRF/XRD

Ion Beam Analysis Techniques

- Elastic Recoil Detection Analysis (ERDA)
- In-situ ion-luminescence (IBIL)
- Nuclear Reaction Analysis (NRA)
- Particle Induced Gamma-ray Emission (PIGE)
- Particle Induced X-ray Emission (PIXE)
- Rutherford Backscattering Spectroscopy (RBS)

Mass spectroscopies

- Thermal Ionization Mass Spectrometry (TIMS) IT
- Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry (ICP-MS)
- Multicollector-Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometer (MC-ICP-MS)
- Thermal Ionization Mass Spectrometry (TIMS) NL
- Isotope ratio mass spectrometry (IRMS)
- Mass spectrometer for stable isotope ratios of light elements
- Mass spectrometry for stable isotope ratios of heavy elements
- Molecular analysis
- Fourier Transform Infrared microimaging
- Mass spectrometry based Omics (Proteomics, Lipidomics, Glycomics, metabolomics)
- for Heritage Science
- Nano LC-MS Liquid Chromatography Mass Spectrometry
- MALDI TOF mass spectrometry
- HRMS High and very high Resolution Mass Spectrometry
- Ancient DNA analysis (aDNA)
- Ion chromatography
- Pyrolysis-Gas chromatography
- 2D size-exclusion / liquid chromatography
- Liquid Chromatography
- Amino acid racemization analysis (AAR)
- Zooarchaeology by Mass Spectrometry (ZooMS)
- Proteomics
- Organic residue analysis (ORA)

Microscopies

- Non Linear Optical Microscopy (NLOM)
- Field emission scanning electron microscope with Energy Dispersive X-ray
- microanalysis System (FE-SEM / EDS)
- Atomic Force Microscopies (AFM)

Molecular analysis

- Fourier Transform Infrared microimaging
- Mass spectrometry based Omics (Proteomics, Lipidomics, Glycomics, metabolomics)
- for Heritage Science
- Nano LC-MS Liquid Chromatography Mass Spectrometry
- MALDI TOF mass spectrometry
- HRMS High and very high-Resolution Mass Spectrometry
- Ancient DNA analysis (aDNA)
- Ion chromatography
- Pyrolysis-Gas chromatography
- 2D size-exclusion / liquid chromatography
- Liquid Chromatography
- Amino acid racemization analysis (AAR)
- Zooarchaeology by Mass Spectrometry (ZooMS)
- Proteomics
- Organic residue analysis (ORA)

Molecular spectroscopies

- Raman Spectroscopy
- FTIR with Attenuated Total Reflectance (ATR)
- Fourier Transform and dispersive Raman microscopy

Neutron techniques

- Neutron Activation Analysis (NAA)
- Neutron-Induced Prompt Gamma-ray Spectroscopy - Neutron Optics and
- Radiography for Material Analysis (NIPS-NORMA)
- Non-destructive testing (NDT) and analysis of archaeological objects and artefacts
- (Neutron-NDT)
- Prompt Gamma Activation Analysis (PGAA)
- Prompt Gamma Activation Imaging (PGAI)
- Small Angle Neutron Scattering (YS-SANS)
- Time of Flight Small Angle Neutron Scattering (FSANS)

Optical spectroscopies

- Laser Induced Fluorescence (LIF)
- Laser Induced Breakdown Spectroscopy (LIBS)
- Spectrometry / Colourimetry

Physical characterization

- Viscometry

Thermal characterization

- Simultaneous Thermogravimetry and Differential Thermal Analysis (TG-DTA)
- Simultaneous Thermal Analysis (STA)
- Thermal gravimetric analysis (TGA)

X-Ray techniques

- 3D computed tomography (XCT)
- Radiography
- Micro X-ray fluorescence mapping (uXRF)
- 3D computed tomography (μ CT)
- 3D computed tomography
- X-Ray Fluorescence (XRF) and (μ XRF)
- X-Ray Powder Diffraction (XRD)
- X-Ray Absorption Spectroscopy (XAS)
- Micro X-Ray Absorption Spectroscopy (μ XAS)
- Time resolved X-Ray Absorption Spectroscopy (XAS 35)
- Deep Ultraviolet Photoluminescence (DUV PL)
- Scanning Transmission X-ray microscopy (STXM)
- X-Ray absorption near edge structure (XANES)
- Optical photothermal spectromicroscopy
- X-Ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS)
- Confocal Raman Microscopy
- Near Edge X-ray Absorption Fine Structure (NEXAFS)
- Energy Dispersive X-ray fluorescence (ED-XRF)
- Scanning Electron Microscopy Energy-Dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (SEM-EDS and EDX)
- Neutron Imaging - Radiography & Tomography

MOLAB

The goal of MOLAB is access to an impressive collection of advanced mobile analytical instrumentation for non-invasive measurements on precious, fragile or immovable objects, archaeological sites and historical monuments. The MOBILE LABORATORY allows its users to implement complex multi-technique diagnostics.

The following list shows the different laboratories and different techniques that can be accessed:

FACILITIES

CY - STARC, APAC laboratories - STARC

DE - RWTH Aachen University Magnetic Resonance Center MARC - RWTH

ES - CSIC-CENIM METAL.es. In-situ metal electrochemical studies for HS - METAL.es

FR - CNRS, Center for Research and Restoration of Museums of France - C2RMF

FR- Laboratoire de recherche des monuments historiques - LRMH

FR - Centre de recherche sur la conservation des collections - CRC

GR - FORTH, Laser Holographic Interferometry, Photonics for CH - IESL

GR - FORTH, IMS, Laboratory of Geophysical Satellite Remote Sensing & Archaeoenvironment - GeoSat ReSeArch Lab

GR - “Ormylia” Foundation, Art Diagnosis Center, iTomography infrastructure-OF ADC

IT- CNR, Optical Lab, Istituto di Ottica, CNR - INO

IT - CNR, SCITEC, Mobile Laboratory - MO LAB

IT - University of Perugia, SMAART - SMAART

IT - CNR, X-ray Lab, Istituto di Scienze del Patrimonio Culturale - X-ray Lab

IT - CNR, AirLab, Istituto di Scienze del Patrimonio Culturale - AirLab

PL - Nicolaus Copernicus University, Institute of Physics, Faculty of Physics, Astronomy and Informatics - NCU

PT - University of Évora, HERCULES Laboratory, - HERCULES

RO - National Institute of R&D in Optoelectronics - INOE 2000

UK - University of Nottingham, Imaging & Sensing for Archaeology, Art History & Conservation – ISAAC

TECHNIQUES

(Multi/hyper spectral) imaging/mapping

- UAV based - VIS multispectral (+RGB) & IRT imagery
- Fluxgate gradiometry
- Scanning Multispectral VIS-NIR reflectography
- Thermography (SIRT)
- NIR hyperspectral imaging (900-2500 nm)
- Macro XRF scanning
- Micro-XRF mapping
- UAV Photogrammetry and aerial multispectral models

2D/3D analysis (close range)

- High resolution digital microscopy
- Optical profilometry
- 3D structure-light scanner and 3D laser scanners
- NMR depth-profiling/relaxometry
- Terahertz imaging
- Digital Holographic Speckle Pattern Interferometry (DHSPI)
- Acoustic tomography
- Optical Coherence Tomography (850 nm)
- Optical Coherence Tomography (1960 nm)

Biomolecular / biodeterioration analysis

- Cytometer, DNA and RNA sequencer, luminometer lumitester, PCR and
- electrophoresis system
- Imaging methods for non-invasive dendrochronology

- Imaging methods for non-invasive dendrochronology

Point analysis

- Total reflection mid/near FTIR
- UV-VIS-NIR reflectance
- UV-VIS-NIR fluorescence
- UV-VIS fluorescence time-decay
- X-Ray Fluorescence (XRF)
- Raman spectroscopy (exc 785 & 1064 nm)
- Micro-Raman (λ exc 532 nm)
- PIXE / low energy XRF
- XRD mapping
- Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy
- Hyphenate XRD/XRF
- Hyphenate LIBS/LIF/Raman
- Confocal XRF mapping

Remote sensing

- UAV-LiDAR
- Ground Penetrating Radar - medium and high frequency antenna
- Ground Penetrating Radar
- Electrical resistivity tomography (ERT)
- Soil resistivity
- Soil conductivity (EMI)
- Magnetic susceptibility measurements
- Laser scanning
- Remote LIBS spectroscopy
- Remote Raman / LIF spectroscopy
- Remote SWIR hyperspectral imaging
- Remote UV LIF spectroscopy
- Remote VIS/NIR spectral imaging for rapid survey of large areas
- Remote VIS/NIR hyperspectral imaging

1.4.4 SURVEY

This study aims to know the resource needs of the paleontological community based on the results of a survey designed in 2 levels, that is, general and detailed questionnaires, aimed at various types of academic and research institutions related to the CFP.

The Survey has been carried out as part of WP7, task 7.5: "Engagement with the paleontological and paleoanthropological community" and is the main component of this feasibility study. The objectives of the survey were to collect as much information as possible, in detail, on various

incorporate new services, addressing the common needs and integration of multiple HS communities especially regarding interoperability and cross-disciplinary applicability.

The Survey was presented as an initial assessment to investigate how this potential initiative could be made viable and operational by contacting selected groups of experts from all fields of Palaeontology. It was also explained that the survey was intended for all potential participants of the IPERION HS initiative who perform or are willing to perform scientific dating analyses on heritage materials. The survey was divided into 2 questionnaires:

- A second 5 minutes, moderately detailed Questionnaire – Part II, to be filled in only if you agreed to the IPERION HS interest question in Part I.
- This survey is meant for all potential participants in IPERION HS - ENGAGEMENT WITH PALAEOANTHROPOLOGY AND PALAEOONTOLOGY COMMUNITY initiative that perform or are willing to perform scientific dating analyses on heritage materials.
- It could be found on the following link: <https://cenieh.limesurvey.net/762425?lang=en>

The original texts to both questionnaires can be read in Appendices A and B.

1.4.6 Dissemination and contributions of the survey

Due to the large number of dating methods available with potential applications in IPERION HS, with the subsequent number of dating laboratories and experts only in Europe, it was decided to substantially reduce this number to a viable survey group. Therefore, only 8 different dating methods were chosen to participate in the survey.

The number of institutions contacted has been 305.

From the questionnaires answered, the following results can summarize the level of contributions and general participation of the 305 experts/laboratories/institutions contacted: 35 inputs were registered; only 30 of them were complete surveys, while 5 were incomplete.

The survey was open for responses from January 8, 2024, to February 22, 2024. A total of 140 questionnaires were received, of which only 30 were fully completed for inclusion in the statistical analysis presented in this final report.

Part I of the survey addressed general questions related to membership and organizational background, as well as general aspects related to knowledge of IPERION HS, and future participation intent if the initiative becomes a reality. Below are the key questions related to the above.

Most of the respondents work in a university (36%), while 31% work in a government institution and 0% in private (commercial) institutions. The rest of contacts (33%) don't say the institution where they belong.

Main professional activity: 53,85% were the Institution's Scientists, Researchers or Experts; 7,69% were the Institution's Head, Director or Leading Scientist; 7,69% were the Institution's Scientist, Researcher or Expert; 7,69% were Graduate or Undergraduate Student; 15,38% have specified their main activity outside the options proposed in the survey, they are Chair of E-RIHS.dk and University Professor and 23,08 have not responded.

General disciplines of academic affiliations: 38,46% Archaeologists; 23,08% are Paleontologists; 15,38% are dedicated to arts and humanities; 7,69% have specified a trained molecular palaeontologist and do a wide variety of proteomics and paleo-proteomics and 23,08% have not responded.

Regional distribution in Europe:

6 Spain; 1 Belgium; 1 Malta; 1 Cyprus; 1 Denmark; 2 Netherlands; 1 Italy; 1 USA; 1 UK-Scotland; 4 Spain.

The rest of the contacts don't say their origin.

Familiarity with IPERION HS initiative: 46,15% positive responses; 30,77% negative responses. Of those familiar with IPERION HS, 7,69 % got to know the initiative through other colleagues while 15,38% go to know from their centre.

Familiarity with the field of HS: 46,15% gave positive responses and only 23,08% gave a negative one. Three specific answers: Development of integrated 3D shape analysis and hyper-spectral imaging, Archaeological Science, more than Heritage Science and work with palaeontological samples but from a research and teaching point of view not in the Heritage field

Interest in participating in the IPERION HS initiative: 100% positive responses.

Interest in QA&QC, e.g., homogenisation, normalisation, laboratory inter-comparisons: 46,15% responded with a yes while 7,69% answered no; 46,15% have not responded and the rest have responded with specific answers: "we are interested to develop protocols for data acquisition and canonical workflows for data processing", "I submitted a (failed) grant to establish collagen isotope standards for archaeology" and "From my part, I consider this aspect an important basis on research on Heritage sciences. I am not confident that institutions are prone to do this."

Interest in becoming a member of IPERION HS Scientific Assessment Committee that evaluates IPERION HS Research Proposals / Service: 46,15% answered yes while 46,15% have not responded.

1.4.7 Survey Data & Key Results

The core of the survey is associated with Questionnaire **Part II**, which only a minority of participants filled out completely.

9. RESEARCH NEEDS: From YOUR PRIORITY AREA OF STUDY , which specific techniques do you need to carry it out? (possible multiple answers. Also you can explain them briefly or make some question

Opción	Cuenta	Porcentaje
Documentary files and databases (AO02)	2	40.00%
Mobile laboratories (AO03)	1	20.00%
Biological analysis (AO04)	0	0.00%
Conservation techniques and preparation methods (AO05)	2	40.00%
Dating (AO06)	2	40.00%
Environmental parameters measurements (AO07)	2	40.00%
Imaging (multiscale and multispectral) (AO08)	1	20.00%
Ion Beam Analysis Techniques (AO09)	0	0.00%
Mass spectroscopies (AO10)	2	40.00%
Microscopies (AO11)	3	60.00%
Molecular analysis (AO12)	2	40.00%
Molecular spectroscopies (AO13)	1	20.00%
Neutron techniques (AO14)	0	0.00%
Optical spectroscopies (AO15)	1	20.00%
Physical characterization (AO16)	0	0.00%
Thermal characterization (AO17)	0	0.00%
X-Ray techniques (AO18)	2	40.00%
Other: (AO19)	0	0.00%

10. Dating Method & Technique. Please specify your institution's type needs. Check all that apply.

Opción	Cuenta	Porcentaje
Numerical Dating (Direct Dating / Radiometric, Isotopic, Geochemical, Trapped Charge). Select : (A149)	0	0.00%
Ar-Ar, K-Ar (AO03)	0	0.00%
TCN (AO04)	0	0.00%
Tephrochronology – Fission Track (AO05)	0	0.00%
14C (AO06)	2	40.00%
U-Series (AO07)	0	0.00%
Luminescence – OSL (AO08)	1	20.00%
Luminescence – TL (AO09)	1	20.00%
Thermo-chronology (U-Th / He or other) (AO10)	0	0.00%
Incremental Dating (Direct Dating: Banded Records). Select: (AO13)	0	0.00%
Palaeomagnetism (AO14)	1	20.00%
Bivalve Sclero-chronology (AO15)	0	0.00%
Coral Chronology (AO16)	0	0.00%
Dendrochronology (AO17)	0	0.00%
Ice Core Chronology (AO18)	0	0.00%
Lichenometry (AO19)	0	0.00%
Speleothem Chronology (AO20)	0	0.00%
Varve Chronology (AO21)	0	0.00%
Relative – Associative – Evaluative Dating (Indirect Dating / Conservation). Select: (AO24)	0	0.00%
Isotope Analysis (Pb, Sr, 34S, 18O, 15N, 13C, 2H, etc.): (AO25)	2	40.00%
Decay Analysis (137Cs, 210Pb, 32Si): (AO26)	0	0.00%
Archaeo-stratigraphy (AO27)	0	0.00%
Bio-stratigraphy (index fossils, micro-fossils, pollen, etc.) (AO28)	1	20.00%
Palaeontology (AO29)	2	40.00%
Palaeosols (AO30)	1	20.00%
Stratigraphy (Geology) (AO31)	0	0.00%
Tephrochronology (AO32)	0	0.00%
Chromatography (AO33)	0	0.00%
DNA – Gene Sequencing (AO34)	0	0.00%
Pigmentation (organic / inorganic) – Patination (AO35)	1	20.00%
Painting Technique (AO36)	1	20.00%
Seriation (AO37)	0	0.00%
Desert Varnish (cation ratio) (AO38)	0	0.00%
Surface Weathering Features (AO39)	0	0.00%
Chemical Analyses (ICPMS, fluorine, ion beam, etc.): (AO40)	2	40.00%
Material Characterisation (x-Ray, XRF, XRD, Raman, etc.): (AO41)	2	40.00%
Microscopy (SEM, CT-Scan, etc.): (AO42)	2	40.00%
Obsidian Hydration (AO43)	0	0.00%

11. General Field of Expertise. When a Dating Service is requested in your institution, within which field does it fall into? . Check all that apply.

Opción	Cuenta	Porcentaje
(SQ001)	0	0.00%
Earth / Environmental Sciences / Natural Heritage (AO03)	0	0.00%
Palaeontology (AO04)	2	40.00%
Palaeo-anthropology (AO05)	1	20.00%
Archaeology (AO06)	2	40.00%
Physical Heritage (e.g. building materials, construction, architecture, etc.) (AO07)	0	0.00%
Cultural Heritage (e.g., art, sculpture, painting, etc.) (AO08)	2	40.00%
Other(s): (AO09)	0	0.00%

12. Number of Samples related to Heritage Sciences. Based on the above, please provide an approximate percentage of samples dated / characterised in your institution per field, within any given year: which samples are from submitters (clients, collaborators, researchers, etc.) with a clear Archaeological – Physical – Cultural Heritage background vs. a more palaeo-environmental origin. Please account for all that applies.

Earth / Environmental Sciences / Natural Heritage: % Samples:	1	20.00%
Palaeontology: % Samples:	0	0.00%
Palaeo-anthropology: % Samples:	2	40.00%
Archaeology: % Samples:	2	40.00%
Physical Heritage:% Samples:	0	0.00%
Cultural Heritage:% Samples:	2	40.00%
Other(s)	1	20.00%

ID	Respuesta
22	The dating method is not listed Amino acid geochronology
23	50
17	all
22	The dating method is not listed Amino acid geochronology
17	all
23	50
27	I am not in charge of the laboratory

13. Authentication – Certification – Verification. Do you and/or your institution need authenticate / certify / verify archaeological- and/or Heritage-related materials?

Earth / Environmental Sciences / Natural Heritage: % Samples:	1	20.00%
Palaeontology: % Samples:	0	0.00%
Palaeo-anthropology: % Samples:	1	20.00%
Archaeology: % Samples:	2	40.00%
Physical Heritage: % Samples:	0	0.00%
Cultural Heritage: % Samples:	1	20.00%
Other(s)	0	0.00%

ID	Respuesta
23	100
22	Isotope standards - collagen

14. Please specify your institution's needs in terms of type of material(s), site(s) and sample(s). Please account for all that applies.

• Materials (e.g., rock; block; sediment; soil; minerals; ceramic; metal; paint; wood; charcoal; paper; teeth; textiles; pollen; bone, etc.):	3	60.00%
* Most needs in:	2	40.00%
* Least needs in:	0	0.00%
• Sites (e.g., caves; marshes; high altitude; underground; castles; churches; painting; sculpture, etc.):	0	0.00%
* Most needs in:	0	0.00%
* Least needs in:	0	0.00%
• Samples (i.e., loose vs. contained sample; types of containers; sediment cores vs. hand specimens, etc.):	0	0.00%
* Most needs in:	0	0.00%
* Least needs in:	0	0.00%

ID	Respuesta
22	Collagen from a range of trophic groups
23	BONES
22	Stable isotope and single amino acid isotope work
23	PALEO ANTHROPOLOGY

15. Types of Services. Please provide the Types of Services your institution request within any given year. Please detail % of samples accepted for each service and their priority within the institution's schedule. Please account for all that applies.

Commercial: % Samples:	Priority:	1	20.00%
Routine Collaboration - Internal Research : % Samples:	Priority:	2	40.00%
Experimental Collaboration - Internal Research: % Samples:	Priority:	2	40.00%
National Laboratory QA Inter-comparisons / Standardizations:% Samples:	Priority:	0	0.00%
International / EU Laboratory QA Inter-comparisons / Standardizations:% Samples:	Priority:	0	0.00%
Calibrations / Verifications / Controls:% Samples:	Priority:	1	20.00%
Maintenance / Mise à point:% Samples:	Priority:	0	0.00%
Others:%	Samples: Priority:	1	20.00%

ID	Respuesta
17	30%
17	60%
23	30
22	20
23	70
17	10%

16. Self-Sufficient Institution. Does your Institution (including Centre / Institution) have all the necessary facilities, equipment and personnel to perform a complete age determination and/or characterisation from A to Z? In other words, do you have a self-sufficient / self-contained institution with no need to reach out for third-party analyses to complete a dating procedure?

Opción	Cuenta	Porcentaje
Yes (AO02)	0	0.00%
No (AO09)	3	60.00%
If No, do you need to sub-contract other laboratories for specific intermediate analyses required for a complete age calculation / characterisation? (AO03)	1	20.00%
Comentarios	1	20.00%
Sin respuesta	1	20.00%

ID	Respuesta
23	NO NEED TO SUB-CONTRACT. IT IS PART OF A COLLABORATICE RESEARCH

17. Equipment Capacity. Describe the type of equipment you typically need for dating/characterization in your institution.

Name :	1	20.00%
Short Description:	0	0.00%
Dating Technique most used for:	0	0.00%
Dating Technique least used for:	0	0.00%

ID	Respuesta
23	MICRO FTIR SPECTROSCOPY, NIR IMAGING

18. Equipment Capacity. In terms of equipment’s use, how much of the following has your institution used and what is its estimated usage within a given year?

Opción	Cuenta	Porcentaje
Specialised Dating Equipment: Quantity: % Usage in 1 year: (AO01)	0	0.00%
Non-Specialised Dating Equipment:Quantity: % Usage in 1 year: (AO03)	0	0.00%
Supplementary equipment needed to achieve an age calculation:Quantity: % Usage in 1 year: (AO04)	1	20.00%
Comentarios	1	20.00%
Sin respuesta	4	80.00%

ID	Respuesta
23	30

19. Turn-around Times. For any material/sample, sent by your institution, what is the average delivery time of the results? Please specify if the values given are in days, months or years.

Best Time:Commercial Service Dating /Research Dating/ Experimental Dating:	1	20.00%
Average Time:Commercial Service Dating/Research Dating/ Experimental Dating:	0	0.00%
Worst Time:Commercial Service Dating/ Research Dating / Experimental Dating:	0	0.00%

ID	Respuesta
23	3 MONTHS

20. Sample Collection Rules – Access. Depending on the dating technique and laboratory, samples may be collected by any individual (expert or non-expert) and sent directly to the laboratory, or require the assistance of an expert for the recovery of any given sample. Do you think that the IPERION HS Palaeoanthropology and Paleontology community should seriously consider these two opposing points of view and allow different types of access to different facilities/laboratories, depending on experience and dating method?

Opción	Cuenta	Porcentaje
YES, would you consider providing your access suggestions / regulations to IPERION HS Palaeoanthropology and Palaeontology community as an example? Yes/No: (AO03)	3	60.00%
NO, do you consider that all accesses to IPERION HS Palaeoanthropology and Palaeontology community should be handled the same way? :Yes/No (AO05)	0	0.00%
Other answer (AO02)	0	0.00%
Comentarios	2	40.00%
Sin respuesta	2	40.00%

ID	Respuesta
22	Need for amino acid geochronology
27	yes

21. Sample Shipping Rules – Access. If a sample (only related to the IPERION HS Palaeoanthropology and Palaeontology community Programme) is to be shipped by your institution, in terms of shipping and handling costs, who should be paying for them?

Opción	Cuenta	Porcentaje
They should be included as part of the IPERION HS Palaeoanthropology and Palaeontology community access package. (AO02)	2	40.00%
The sender, whoever s/he might be, at their own cost. (AO03)	1	20.00%
The recipient laboratory, at their own cost. (AO04)	0	0.00%
Comentarios	0	0.00%
Sin respuesta	2	40.00%

ID	Respuesta
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22. Laboratory & Data Location – Access. For several types of Dating Techniques, it is imperative for the laboratory to be / operate in the vicinity of the research project, sample / material collection location. . Is that a requisite for your Institution?

Opción	Cuenta	Porcentaje
Yes (AO01)	0	0.00%
No (AO02)	2	40.00%
Comentarios	0	0.00%
Sin respuesta	3	60.00%

ID	Respuesta
----	-----------

23. IPERION HS Seal of Quality – Brand. Would you encourage the development or be interested in the branding of IPERION HS as a sign/seal of quality, prestige and certification?

Opción	Cuenta	Porcentaje
Yes (AO01)	1	20.00%
If yes, would you be willing to participate in homogenisation, normalisation, standardization experiments and routines, as well as QC-QA inter-comparisons involving laboratories within the same dating domain, to improve and preserve IPERION HS quality? (AO03)	2	40.00%
NO, please provide a short explanation: (AO04)	1	20.00%
Comentarios	3	60.00%
Sin respuesta	1	20.00%

ID	Respuesta
17	yes
22	We do not offer a facility.
23	YES

24. Funding Capacity. In general terms, please specify your Institution’s general funding scheme, i.e., how does your institution run, considering the following types of funding and to which percentage.

Commercial service income: % Funds:	1	20.00%
Consultancy: % Funds:	0	0.00%
Research funds (national and/or international grants): % Funds:	3	60.00%
Industry contracts: % Funds:	0	0.00%
In-kind funds:% Funds:	0	0.00%
Private and/or philanthropic donations: % Funds:	1	20.00%
Regular Government input/income/contracts: % Funds:	2	40.00%
Core funding (internal): % Funds:	1	20.00%
Other(s): Please specify.: % Funds:	0	0.00%

ID	Respuesta
22	1
22	69
23	70
23	30
22	30

25. Institution Funding Potential. Would your Institution be able or willing to self-fund experiments, collaborations and/or research?

Opción	Cuenta	Porcentaje
Yes (AO01)	0	0.00%
No (AO02)	2	40.00%
If yes, please specify. Please account for all that applies: 1 project every few years / 1 project per year / More than 1 project per year (AO03)	1	20.00%
Comentarios	2	40.00%
Sin respuesta	2	40.00%

ID	Respuesta
17	partially
22	These would have to be tied to a grant.

26. Other comments or queries

Opción	Cuenta	Porcentaje
Opción	1	20.00%
Sin respuesta	4	80.00%

ID	Respuesta
22	It would be useful for geochron, to undertake a series of Blind Studies. I am planning a grant to explore dating of (ostrich) eggshell. These are from worldwide sites. It would be interesting to compare the extent of protein degradation as a molecular clock with other methods and thus develop standards.

1.4.8 1.4. Survey Barriers

Several difficulties and issues were encountered since the creation of the survey. The main points are summarised below:

- Large number of dating methods: There are many dating methods applicable in HS. The same goes for its labs and related experts.
- Many institutions contacted do not want to answer simple questions about the number of samples handled for different services (for example, commercial, collaborative or internally driven research projects) and the approximate percentage breakdown, once they seem interested in participating.
- The purpose of the “what kind of service” exercise is to demonstrate that most institutions require multiple sources of income to remain viable and survive in the long term. This can potentially affect productivity and collaboration efforts. Many inquiries at other institutions

have gone unanswered, demonstrating the difficulty in obtaining this or any other type of information from chronology facilities.

- Many institutions have a strict sense of exclusivity, a "closed door" attitude and competition, so they may not be open to being part of the survey, agree to promote our "Service" and much less collaborate.
- Most institutions that may have established rules for "service", specifically with external services in mind such as commercial work and even certain types of collaboration.

1.4.9 1.5. **Final comments and suggestions**

The number of projects, the number of samples, the type of access and the type of financing seem to be the most important but questionable factors associated with the use of IPERION HS services. A greater general consensus is needed on the type of services demanded. However, the general impression towards this IPERION HS initiative is very positive.

1.4.10 **Recommendations: Key Concepts to Define**

Prior to the creation or during the initial stages of formation of IPERION HS, it is advisable to define some key concepts related to this survey. Clarification of these concepts would much improve the implementation and success of UCS. Some of these concepts are:

- The *age range* of HS is still not defined and is still debatable. What should be the lower and upper limits of HS time range?
 - Lower Limit: historical? Industrial Revolution? Anthropocene? 100 years ago? Yesterday?
 - Upper Limit: beginning of HE (i.e., 8-10 Ma) or only since the genus Homo appeared 2 Ma ago?
- Number of *dating methods* to include in the UCS:
 - Should all dating methods summarised in this Task 7.5 be included in the survey?
 - Most of them have related laboratories in Europe, but not all laboratories may want to be involved in IPERION HS.
 - All methods included should overlap in terms of time range among techniques. These overlapping age ranges should be clearly defined.
- All the different options of the *service*, i.e., full in-house dating, partial in-house dating, dating with training of students/technicians, full dating analysis included, partial dating analysis (i.e., cheaper rates), etc.
- *Language proficiency*:
 - English as official language of communication at all levels, for all services, for all reports & documents.
 - Good knowledge of English should be obliged for participation at any level and in any type of service.
 - Reason: fast and effective communication should exist among all institutions / laboratories involved, back and forth with the main frame of IPERION HS. There should be no reason for miscommunication.

- Minimum and maximum number of *participating institutions* per dating method and discipline:
 - Institutions depend on several factors such as specialization of each one, user demand and capacity to accept samples / services, number of personnel, geographical coverage.
 - These issues are known to each individual laboratory and not necessarily to e.g. WP7.
- Number of *experts* involved per institution.
 - We need to start from the basis that an empty institution cannot be run by itself or offer services. Hence the importance of the experts involved in the initiative and the IPERION HS process.
 - The amount of experts ensures the quality of both the service and the results.

1.5 Conference, meetings and similar events

1.5.1 Webinar “Paleontology research and IPERION HS” (2021)

In November 2021, we presented a webinar to the Palaeontology community, answers the

Webinar #07 / November, 9th 2021

PALAEONTOLOGY RESEARCH & IPERION HS

MARINA MARTÍNEZ DE PINILLOS GONZÁLEZ, BELÉN NOTARIO, JOAQUÍN ARROYO-CABRALES & RUBÉN MANZANILLA-LÓPEZ

Webinar 7: Palaeontology

The webinar answers the questions arising from the Palaeontology community in relations with a better knowledge, interpretation, authentication, preservation and restoration of heritage.

The focus is on what IPERION HS can offer to the Palaeontology community to answer these research needs.

[Watch the video](#)

questions arising from the Palaeontology community in relations with a better knowledge, interpretation, authentication, preservation, and restoration of heritage. The focus is on what IPERION HS can offer to the Palaeontology community to answer these research needs.

(Link: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=CYzuK4jGKjc>)

This webinar in the [#HSAcademy](#) series was presented by Belén Notario (National Center for Research on Human Evolution, Spain) and Joaquín Arroyo-Cabrales (National Institute of Anthropology and History, Mexico). Belén Notario explores how Micro-Computed Tomography can be used in the field of palaeontology to examine different human and animal remains. Joaquín Arroyo-Cabrales discusses their latest discovery – a large mammoth graveyard that includes more than 600 specimens. The webinar was guest-moderated by Marina Martínez de

Fig. 11 Advertising of the webinar “Paleontology research and IPERION HS”

Pinillos González (National Center for Research on Human Evolution, Spain) with the aim to explore the potential of IPERION HS facilities to address research questions posed by palaeontology community.

1.5.2 Webinar “New synchrotron light sources and paleontological studies (2022)”

In February 2022, we presented a Webinar to the paleontology community about new synchrotron light sources and paleontological studies.

This webinar presents the new light sources available at the 4th generation synchrotron in Brazil and tells the investigation of materials in paleontology with the new approach named nanopaleometry. The idea is to understand the oldest fossil records on the planet so that they can be used as models of what to search on Mars, for evidence of past life.

(Link: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=k0cjkhgj0jo>)

This webinar in the [#HSAcademy](#) series was presented by Douglas Galante (Synchrotron National Laboratory LNLS/CNPEM, Brazil) and provides an overview of new synchrotron light sources applied to paleontological studies. Brazil is now at the forefront of synchrotron science, being one of the few countries to be operating a 4th generation synchrotron machine, Sirius. This type of equipment, coupled to very advanced beamlines and experimental stations allows the investigation of materials with an unprecedented resolution and sensitivity, making it possible to go down to the atomic scale. With this, the group has been studying the paleontological record at the nanoscale, using a variety of analytical techniques, in an approach called nanopaleometry. The webinar was moderated by Matija Strlič (University of Ljubljana, Slovenia, and University College London, UK) with the aim to explore the potential of IPERION HS facilities to address research questions posed by palaeontology community.

Fig. 12 Advertising material for the webinar on new synchrotron light sources

1.5.3 1st Training Camp in Burgos

From the 11th until July 15th, 2022, the first HS Academy Summer School was held in Burgos, Spain. The venue was at the CENIEH (Centro Nacional de Investigación sobre la Evolución Humana) and the

Atapuerca UNESCO world heritage fossil sites, whose Atapuerca Research Team (EIA) is made up of nearly 300 specialists of 22 different nationalities from 30 different disciplines.

The 1st Training Camp was open to a wide audience interested in learning material characterization and dating techniques applied to palaeontological and palaeoanthropological heritage. The Training Camp was structured around 5 days of general lectures and specific case studies that included fieldwork session and laboratory analysis. The case studies were addressed in small groups of 5 people maximum and focused on the application and use of different FIXLAB facilities. They involved direct interactions with the reference expert scientist for each technique, encouraging thorough discussions and constructive debate amongst the participants.

Fig. 13 Photos taken during the 1st Training Camp

The Training Camp had excellent feedback with a rating of 9.62 (out of 10) and received great comments. Just to highlight one: “Lab visits, practical sessions and field sessions incredible experiences that I never expected and experienced before. This is a lifetime experience. I am happy, satisfied and thankful for having this opportunity!”

This event isn't yet a training activity, on the last day we delivered a survey that, in addition to revealing the degree of satisfaction with the sessions, has allowed us to know the needs that scientists will find in researchers within the field of paleontology and that, globally; we have classified as follows:

1. Fundamental continuous interrelationship with other researchers.
2. Realization of practical sessions in the field periodically and in small groups.
3. Formulation of specific protocols for collecting samples in the field, and other procedures.
4. Knowledge of available equipment and its potential applications to the different lines of research.
5. Holding conferences on different processes within paleontology, such as dental anthropology, mortuary practices, paleopathology, complemented by practical sessions.

1.5.4 Lecture “Timing the spread of creative innovations by Homo Sapiens and Neanderthals using the radiocarbon dating method”

In January 2023 we presented a new Lecture focused to the palaeontology community: Timing the spread of creative innovations by Homo sapiens and Neanderthals using the radiocarbon dating method .

This lecture in the [#HSAcademy](#) “Current Topics in Heritage Science” series was delivered by Sahra Talamo on January 19th, 2022, from 3 to 4 pm (CET). She spoke about radiocarbon dating and its role in the study of human evolution. She addressed how we can overcome the fire of destroying precious objects and directly date them using the updated radiocarbon pretreatment, the latest AMS instrumental advances, and the new IntCal20 calibration curve.

(Link: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Rg8XPOcgA0Y>)

The 5th webinar in the 'Current Topics in Heritage Science' Lecture series 2022 was presented by Sahra Talamo (University of Bologna, Italy). She spoke about radiocarbon dating and its role in the study of human evolution. The artistic expression, like any kind of personal ornaments, is associated with the emergence of cultural innovations introduced by Homo sapiens in the Initial Upper Palaeolithic, as demonstrated by the earliest unsophisticated manipulation of animal teeth in Bulgaria, around 46,000 years BP. Similar behaviour is documented in Southwestern France within the Neanderthal groups. On the other hand, the elaborate and highly standardized manufacturing processes are recognized in the Early Aurignacian culture, done by Homo sapiens, prior to 40,000 years BP. The cultural innovation and the production of highly symbolic values from complex technological processes, like figurines or punctate decoration objects, started to be recognised across Europe. The question around the beginning of the artistic explosion and the timing of these behavioural innovations is still challenging, especially if precious and unique objects will be damaged. In this lecture, Sahra Talamo explains about how we can overcome the fire of destroying precious objects and directly date them using the updated radiocarbon pretreatment, the latest AMS instrumental advances, and the new IntCal20 calibration curve. Only with these new developments we can increase precision in establishing the true age of the item itself and fill the gap in the most intriguing puzzle about symbolic behaviour and modern

Fig. 14: Promotional material of the lecture by Sahra Talamo

cognition in Human Evolution. The lecture was moderated by Diego Quintero Balbás (Cnr - National Institute of Optics, CNR-INO, Italy), one of the emerging professionals in the organising committee of the 'Current Topics in Heritage Science' lecture series. The monthly lectures will be part of the IPERION HSAcademy and will continue the mission of the now well-established webinars but with more focus on fundamental aspects of heritage science, such as techniques and methodologies, as well as specific heritage typologies and many other topics of interest to the field. This video reflects only the author's view and the Agency, and the European Commission are not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

1.5.5 Conference at CENIEH (2023)

In July 2023, we presented a conference on the importance of new ways of disseminating scientific

Fig. 15 Post on X about the conference

research in the frame of the project IPERION HS.

Centro Nacional de Investigación sobre la Evolución Humana - CENIEH organized in Burgos a conference in collaboration with other highly relevant entities in the field such as the Museum of Human Evolution, Atapuerca Foundation, and IPHES CERCA, as a way of diffusion of IPERION HS among the scientists of the Heritage Science domain. Participants could also visit the UNESCO archaeological site of

Atapuerca.

The basis of all scientific research is in infrastructures sharing knowledge and expertise!

The conference was moderated by Juan Luis Arsuaga, Professor of Paleontology at Complutense University, Madrid. Director of the UCM-ISCIH Center on Human Evolution and Behavior. Co-director of Atapuerca Unesco Site, Scientific Director of the Museum of Human Evolution in Burgos, Francesc Gasco, doctor in Paleontology, Professor at the Isabel I University and collaborator of BE-UNED, Ignacio Martin Lerma, Professor of Prehistory at the University of Murcia and Vice-Dean of the Faculty of Letters of Murcia and Marga Sánchez Romero, archaeologist and professor and vice-

rector of the University of Granada and organized by the Center for Human Evolution - CENIEH, Atapuerca Foundation and the Catalan Institute of Human Paleology and Social Evolution - IPHES.

Day 1: Cenieh laboratories visit and conference

“Conference on the Social networks: new ways of scientific dissemination to access and share knowledge in all fields.

Iperion is a pioneer in this aspect, since its large network of collaborating institutions allows it to reach an unlimited number of people around the world through all the communication channels that exist. It offers new analysis methodologies in all cultural heritage at a global level, mainly in three senses:

1. It makes large infrastructures, mobile and permanent, available to the entire scientific community, which work in different models to preserve, conserve cultural heritage.
2. Training, training of people from all over the planet,
3. Diffusion,

“ The basis of all scientific research is in infrastructures and knowledge.”

Day 2: Visit at the Unesco Atapuerca sites.

General wrap discussion with attendees on site with nearly 300 specialists of 22 different nationalities from 30 different disciplines

All events were disseminated by Twitter and YouTube.

Although it is considered a study of knowledge of needs, it could become one of the most important initiatives within IPERION HS, because of the importance of being able to respond to the real needs of resources that certain research communities need, as is the case of the PPC, allows to involve the participation of new institutions belonging to these communities in this initiative, since there is still a large part of these institutions that prefer to compete instead of collaborating.

We also held a well-received event for scientific dissemination organized in Burgos by CENIEH, the days 29/30th September 2023 into the " XIV European Researchers Night ", we held an event called "European Corner" to publicize the IPERION HS project.

The National Center for Research on Human Evolution (CENIEH) organized its XIV European Night of Researchers, a day full of activities whose objective is to show, share and bring together the work of scientists and technologists, which given the research nature of the Center, It has a very wide diffusion in the paleontological and archaeological field.

The event was a great success in terms of visits and our space was undoubtedly one of the most consulted activities, especially applauded and consulted, thereby achieving great dissemination of the IPERION HS structure.

**LA NOCHE EUROPEA
DE LOS INVESTIGADOR@S**

ORIGEN CASTILLA Y LEÓN, DESTINO MUNDO

European Corner

IPERION HS

Integrating Platforms for the European
Research Infrastructure ON Heritage
Science

Did you know that the National Research Center for Human Evolution is part of Iperion HS? This project offers training and access to a wide range of high-level scientific instruments, methodologies, data and tools to advance knowledge and innovation in heritage science.

Come and meet the great European projects!

Síguenos en www.cenieh.es

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Centro Nacional de Investigación
en Evolución Humana

Infraestructuras
Científicas y Técnicas
Singulares

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CENIEH

GOBIERNO
DE ESPAÑA

MINISTERIO
DE CIENCIA
E INNOVACIÓN

FECYT
INNOVACIÓN

Fig. 16 Poster of the conference

Fig. 17 A picture of the event in Burgos

All events were disseminated by X Twitter, Instagram, YouTube, in local TV and streaming.

1.5.6 Lecture on Chronological Tools (2023)

Lecture #03 / December 14th, 2023

CHRONOLOGICAL TOOLS:
DATING HUMAN
EVOLUTIONARY HISTORY

ALTUG HASOZBEK

Edition 2
HSAcademy
Current Topics

Lecture 3 (2023-24) :
**Chronological Tools: Dating
Human Evolutionary History**

The 3rd lecture of the 2nd edition "Current Topics in Heritage Science" series was delivered by Altug Hazosbek on December 14, at 3 pm (CET). The speaker introduced the most advanced state-of-the-art techniques, including Optically Stimulated Luminescence (OSL), Electron Spin Resonance (ESR), and in detail Uranium-Thorium (U-Th) dating. Altug explained the whole process from sample collection, and methodological considerations, to the associated instrumental analyses. Furthermore, the lecture was complemented by presenting real-world case studies, particularly from the CENIEH (National Center for Research on Human Evolution) and the Atapuerca site in Burgos, Spain.

The 2nd edition of "Current Topics in Heritage Science" was presented by Dr. Altug Hasozbek (expert at National Center for Research on Human Evolution in Burgos, Spain) in December, 2023. A new Lecture focused on the Palaeontology community. In this episode, we explore cutting-edge inorganic dating methods and advances in accuracy and precision for the study of human evolution. Altug Hasozbek focused on state-of-the-art techniques including Optically Stimulated Luminescence (OSL), Electron Spin Resonance (ESR) and Uranium-Thorium (U-Th) dating. Real-world case studies from CENIEH and the Atapuerca site in Burgos, Spain, provide valuable insights. In addition, the discussion covers the complete process from sample collection to instrumental analyses, and addresses future prospects and potential advances in these scientific methods. Altug Hasozbek is a distinguished geochemist (PhD), currently contributing his expertise at the U-Series Lab, which is a

Fig. 18 Promotion of the lecture part of the CENIEH (National Center for Research on Human Evolution) in Burgos, Spain. He

specializes in isotope geochemistry in understanding geological and environmental processes through isotopic studies. His work primarily involves the use of instruments such as ICP-MS (Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry), MC-ICP-MS (Multi-Collector Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry), and TIMS (Thermal Ionization Mass Spectrometry) for radiometric dating.

[Link: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=FJwb3JEaulc](https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=FJwb3JEaulc)

Over the past decade, advancements in inorganic dating methods, backed by cutting-edge instrumentation, have faced rigorous scrutiny. This rigorous evaluation has fostered enhancements in both the accuracy and precision of these techniques, spanning from low to high spatial applications in human evolution research.

This in turn has facilitated the acquisition of absolute age determinations. Within this context, this presentation delves into the dating methodologies tailored specifically for samples pertinent to human evolution studies.

This lecture will briefly spotlight state-of-the-art techniques, including Optically Stimulated Luminescence (OSL), Electron Spin Resonance (ESR), and in detail Uranium-Thorium (U-Th) dating. This lecture will encompass the complete process from sample collection, methodological considerations, to the associated instrumental analyses. Furthermore, these techniques will be covered by presenting real-world case studies, particularly from the CENIEH and the Atapuerca site in Burgos, Spain.

Future prospects and potential advancements in these dating methods will also be explored and discussed.

In this lectures, Dr. Altug Hasozbek explained us:

- The appropriate dating technique for the sample.
- Strategies for handling challenging samples in dating methods.
- Insights into the accuracy and precision of dating techniques in human evolution research.

The topics he covered:

- Fundamentals of OSL, ESR, and U-Series dating techniques.
- Use of dating methods in human evolution studies.
- Expanded uncertainties in radiometric dating.
- CENIEH's strategies for dating valuable samples.

1.6 T7.6 Engagement with the archaeology community

Task Leader: UCL/HEL

1.6.1 Description of the task 7.6

The archaeology community, including the related fields of zooarchaeology, archaeobotany, archaeotechnology etc., is in many ways a logical extension of the community of users generally already involved in the EU trans-national access projects in the fields of heritage and conservation sciences. However, the field of archaeology has specific needs and research questions that are related to archaeological sites in the context of modern land use change. Such research is thus often related to spatial planning processes. Furthermore, understanding of archaeological context can be used to develop an understanding of the lives of past communities, their social and organisational structures, migration and exchange – all topics relevant to modern social cohesion. Diversity of archaeological evidence is enormous, ranging from whole landscapes and submerged marine environments to microscopic biota. Evidence is often highly scattered and hugely complex computational tools need to be deployed in order to develop a temporal and associational understanding of the components. We will develop joint sessions and events with the European Association of Archaeologists, the European Archaeological Council, and other similar associations, in order to develop and grow a strong user base in the future, and to realise greater public benefit. In particular, we will explore the potential for much closer engagement between development-funded archaeologists and the capabilities afforded by heritage science (and by IPERION HS specifically), based on analysis of the techniques available compared with evidence for their general uptake and use in archaeological excavation (D7.6)

1.6.2 Explanation of the work carried out per T7.6

1.6.2.1 Raising Awareness

For the first two and a half years of the project engagement with the archaeological community focused on raising awareness and the opportunities it afforded for Trans-National Access (TNA) to Heritage Science Infrastructure and for collaborative research and capacity building as laid out in D7.2 Detailed engagement plan for new user's communities.

This was achieved through social media, by presenting talks on the project at conferences and through articles published in the newsletters and bulletins produced by archaeological institutions and Special Interest Groups. In addition, the project members and partners promoted the project during training events, at conferences and as part of visits to providers' institutions by a wide range of stakeholders.

Major raising awareness activities that were carried out are:

1. Chartered Institute for Archaeologists (CIfA) online conference –Paper presented in April 2021 - 40 attendees at 'live' event but all those registered for the conference (nearly 500) could view the recording of the paper.
2. Article in Historic England Research News 18 <https://historicengland.org.uk/whats-new/research/investing-in-scientific-research/> in September 2021 - 15 thousand subscribers and more on social media (circa 30K)
3. Short article in PAST, the newsletter of Prehistoric Society <https://www.prehistoricsociety.org/publications/past/101> in Summer 2022 -2000 subscribers.

Following the closing of the 5th call for TNA (30th September 2022) focus switched to promoting the project using three methods:

1. Promotion of the HS-Academy webinars (<https://www.iperionhs.eu/academy-events/>)
2. Direct contact with researchers via online email discussion (JISCMail) lists. This was carried out when researchers asked questions on these discussion lists about how they might get funding for a particular piece of research or how they might answer a particular research question.
3. Providers directly contacting researchers or promoting their own Heritage Science Infrastructure to target groups.

1.6.2.2 Developing and growing a strong user base for the future

This element of the work carried out focussed on a workshop organised by Ms Gill Campbell, Dr. Marta Castillejo, and Dr. Canan Çakırlar at the European Association of Archaeologists (EAA) Conference Budapest 2nd September 2022.

This workshop sought the views of archaeologists on 'what they want from a distributed science infrastructure'. It posed a series of questions that were explored in the run-up and during the session (See Table 8.1)

There were 10 in-person attendees at the workshop session, but wider engagement was achieved beyond the workshop at other conference sessions and through networking activities (2000 delegates).

Questions

1. Objects and Materials
Thinking about the objects/ materials you or others study what do you want to know about them?
What techniques do you already know about and have access to?
What is missing?
2. Site and Landscapes
Thinking about the sites/ landscapes you or others study what do you want to know about them?
What techniques do you already know about and have access to?
What is missing?
3. Data Management and Data Sharing
How do you find /access comparative datasets in your work?
Do you have the skills and resources to make your data FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable)?
Complete the following: I wish there was a database of ...

Table 8.1 Questions posed at the EAA workshop in Budapest September 2022

Workshop attendees expressed the view that they knew about a wide range of techniques to study objects and materials and did not feel anything was missing. They were principally interested in provenance, composition, survival of biomolecules, and long-term conservation (archives).

Similar responses were obtained for sites and landscapes. However here the principal concerns centred around the understanding of climate change. There is a need to build mechanisms for a cross-disciplinary approach to monitor the impacts of climate change on archaeological sites and historic landscapes, including the integration of different remote sensing techniques, use of documentary data, and landscape management/ climate adaptation.

Most of the discussion centred around data management and data sharing. There is a need to better signpost research outputs and documentation, particularly for those working in the commercial sector (development-funded archaeologists). As the creators of data that is often used by research projects to explore overarching questions about our shared past, development-funded archaeologists want their contributions to be recognised. One of the ways in which this can be achieved is through the production of citable datasets with DOIs. This leads on to a desire for training on how to deposit the data they produce and make it FAIR, as well as the need for the development of digital infrastructures such as ARIDANE RI (<https://www.ariadne-research-infrastructure.eu/>) and E-RHIS Digilab (<https://www.e-rihs.gr/digilab/>).

1.6.2.3 Analysis

Data about the new user groups was collected from the 3rd call for access proposals onwards when the worst effects of the pandemic were over. There was an excellent take up of opportunities for Trans-National Access by the Archaeology Community with proposals forming between 26%-44% of the total number of proposals. The response to the 5th call (closed 30 September 2022) was especially pronounced with applications from the archaeology community comprising 42% of the total proposals received. This illustrates the impact of the short article in PAST, and the EAA conference workshop. It may also reflect the success of the training camp held in July 2022 in Burgos, Spain. While this training camp was targeted at the Palaeoanthropology and Palaeontology community some of this community may identify themselves as archaeologists and therefore will be accounted for in this grouping rather than palaeontology.

Similar considerations apply to the disciplines covered under the 'other' grouping. Material scientists may identify themselves as material scientists first, even though they may be working on archaeological materials. This may also apply to natural history conservation, numismatics and archaeometry.

There was a fall-off in the proportion of proposals received from the Archaeology Community for the 6th call, 26% of the total. This likely relates to a combination of two factors. Firstly, the last of the major engagement activities took place in autumn 2022 and no further new initiatives were planned beyond promoting the HS Academy webinars and promotions at meetings/ conferences by the project partners. Secondly, there was uncertainty over whether the project would be extended and therefore whether users would have time to carry out their access requests within their own project time and work programme constraints.

Once the extension of the project was confirmed and a 7th call was announced this trend was reversed and 44% of the total proposals received came from the Archaeology Community. This percentage increase is likely to reflect users putting in proposals once the extended access window was confirmed but also shows that direct contact with users, including engagement with online discussion forums increases awareness and removes barriers by making potential users aware of who can apply for access. For example, that access was not restricted to those based in academic institutions and that individuals could apply.

It also illustrates the importance of continuing to carry out awareness-raising activities over the full length of the project to reinforce and build a strong user base.

2 Evaluation and conclusions

We can evaluate the success of the commitment of all new groups taking into account the following indicators:

- Number of new user requests
- Ratio of new user requests compared to the total number of requests
- Success rate of new users when requesting transnational access
- Success rate of new users requesting cross-border access compared to established users
- Engagement of new users with social networks, webinars, etc.
- Number of academic projects (master's, doctorate, published articles, etc.) resulting from new collaborations

The long-term objective, after the end of the IPERION HS project, would be to develop performance indicators understandable for new user groups close to those of the already established scientific communities and to closely monitor the feedback, which could be pursued with E-RIHS.

According to records obtained automatically based on access to the IPERION HS websites or The Commitment Plan should be continuous over time beyond IPERION HS.

We can summarize these indicators as follows:

- More than 50 local, national, European and international organizations contacted I have intervened
- 140 events at IPERION HS
- >34,000 attendees
- Different strategies have been used for different communities
- Conferences, workshops, newsletters, and training, all with great follow-up.
- It is worth noting that online events attract large audiences.
- The doctoral school and training camps are popular and appreciated among attendees.
- Online conferences and webinars are a good way to interact with all communities.
- We must be aware that different groups of users require different methods of participation and
- Heritage science includes professionals from different types of careers who need different support.
- Finally, it should be noted that there is a demand for flexible and permanent training among all users of all disciplines.

In the following graphs we want to show the evolution of transactional access, differentiated by disciplines, throughout the life of the project.

They show separately the accesses of the 6th and last calls and those of the 7th and last to identify the impact that all the actions carried out during the validity of IPERION HS could have had.

SUBMITTED PROPOSALS

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Fig. 19 Proposals submitted

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IPERION HS

PLATFORMS REQUEST ACCESS ACROSS THE 7 CALLS

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Fig. 20 Platforms request access across the seven calls

IPERION HS

USER GROUP LEADER

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Fig. 21 User Group leaders

USER GROUP LEADER (1st – 6th call)

Fig. 22 User Group leader (1st - 6th call)

USER GROUP LEADER (7th call)

Fig. 23 User Group leader (7th call)

USER GROUP LEADER (1st – 6th call)

Fig. 24 User Group Leader (call 1-6)

USER GROUP LEADER (7th call)

Fig. 25 User group Leader (call 7)

IPERION HS NEW COMMUNITIES (1st – 6th call)

- “Other”
- Archaeometry
- Carbonate Sedimentology
- Chemistry
- Conservation
- Conservation science
- Heritage science
- Natural History Conservation
- Numismatic
- Physics
- Geology
- Material Science
- Geoscience

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Fig. 26 New communities (call 1-6)

IPERION HS SCIENTIFIC DISCIPLINES (1st – 6th call)

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Fig. 27 Scientific disciplines (call 1-6)

SCIENTIFIC DISCIPLINES (7th call)

Fig. 28 Scientific disciplines (call 7)

Without a doubt, we can affirm that the project has been a success, despite the global stoppage caused by the COVID-19 pandemic shortly after it began. It has been possible to unite, strengthen and fraternize scientific institutions of heritage sciences, attracting other institutions from disciplines that were not previously well identified within heritage science, such as archaeology, paleontology, building conservation, social and human sciences.

Appendix A – Online Survey: Questionnaire Part I (text)

Cenieh 2024: Member of IPERION HS
Program: Palaeoanthropology and palaeontology community

General Institution Aspects

Name: _____
 Institution: _____
 Faculty / Field of Science: _____
 Institute / University / Centre: _____
 Location & Country: _____
 E-mail: _____

Questionnaire Part I: General Institution Aspects

General Institution Aspects

1. In which capacity are you filling out this questionnaire? *Please specify – chose one.*

Choose one of the following answers.

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Centre
- Institute
- Faculty Director or Dean
- Institution's Head / Director / Leading Scientist
- Institution's Scientist / Researcher / Expert
- Institution's Manager / Head Technician / Head Analyst
- Institution's Technician / Analyst
- Post-Doc / Research Fellow / Visiting Expert
- Graduate / Undergraduate Student

Comment on your choice here:

2. How do you mainly work (single choice):

Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Conservator/Restorer
- Curator (Please specify collection type)
- Archaeologist
- Paleontologist
- Architect/Conservation Architect
- Natural Science Researcher
- Arts and humanities researcher
- Archivist/Librarian
- Academic with research interests (please specify field) _____
- Other: _____

Comment on your choice here:

3. Are you or were you already familiar with the IPERION HS initiative? If Yes, Through which channels?

Comment only when you choose an answer.

Please choose all that apply and provide a comment:

- Yes
- No
- From other colleagues in the field
- From your Centre / Institute / University
- From conferences and meetings
- From the news, website, social media
- Others (please specify):

4. Are you with the field of Heritage Sciences?

Choose one of the following answers.

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No
- If yes, please fill out the follow-up Questionnaire – Part II, for more detailed questions regarding your institution services and resources.
- If no, please provide a short explanation:

Comment on your choice here:

5. Are you and your institution interested in participating in the IPERION HS initiative?

Choose one of the following answers.

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No
- If no, please provide a short explanation.

Comment on your choice here:

6. Would you and your institution be willing to partake in any protocol homogenisation, normalisation experiments, or laboratory inter-comparison initiatives promoted by IPERION HS, involving other institutions or laboratories within the same dating domain?

Choose one of the following answers.

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

Comment on your choice here:

7. Would you and your institution willing to partake in quality control & quality management assessments, and standardisation initiatives promoted by IPERION HS involving other institutions within similar dating domains?

Choose one of the following answers.

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

Comment on your choice here:

8. Would you, or an expert within your institution team, be willing to be considered for a probable/eventual Scientific Assessment Committee evaluating IPERION HS Research Proposals / Services or Access Requests related exclusively to the Palaeoanthropology and palaeontology community?

Choose one of the following answers.

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- If not, could you please provide the name of an expert you consider optimal for this position (outside your institution)

Comment on your choice here:

Appendix B – Online Survey: Questionnaire Part II (text)

Questionnaire Part II
Cenieh 2024: Member of IPERION HS
Program: Palaeoanthropology and Palaeontology community

Here, specific details concerning your institution will be asked to gather as much precise information concerning both the feasibility of the creation of an **IPERION HS Palaeoanthropology and palaeontology community** programme and the potential for participation and involvement of your institution in such programme.

This questionnaire is meant for all potential institution participants who perform or are willing to perform scientific dating analyses on Heritage materials.

Please fill in as accurately as possible, rounding numbers as close as possible to reality.

9. RESEARCH NEEDS: From YOUR PRIORITY AREA OF STUDY, which specific techniques do you need to carry it out? (Possible multiple answers. Also, you can explain them briefly or ask some question.

Check all that apply.

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Documentary files and databases
- Mobile laboratories
- Biological analysis
- Conservation techniques and preparation methods
- Dating
- Environmental parameters measurements
- Imaging (multiscale and multispectral)
- Ion Beam Analysis Techniques
- Mass spectroscopies
- Microscopies
- Molecular analysis
- Molecular spectroscopies
- Neutron techniques
- Optical spectroscopies
- Physical characterization
- Thermal characterization
- X-Ray techniques
- Other:

10. Dating Method & Technique.

Please specify your institution's type needs.

Check all that apply.

Please choose **all** that apply:

Numerical Dating (Direct Dating / Radiometric, Isotopic, Geochemical, Trapped Charge). Select :

- Ar-Ar, K-Ar

- TCN
- Tephrochronology – Fission Track
- ¹⁴C
- U-Series
- Luminescence – OSL
- Luminescence – TL
- Thermo-chronology (U-Th / He or other)

Incremental Dating (Direct Dating: Banded Records). Select:

- Palaeomagnetism
- Bivalve Sclero-chronology
- Coral Chronology
- Dendrochronology
- Ice Core Chronology
- Lichenometry
- Speleothem Chronology
- Varve Chronology

Relative – Associative – Evaluative Dating (Indirect Dating / Conservation). Select:

- Isotope Analysis (Pb, Sr, ³⁴S, ¹⁸O, ¹⁵N, ¹³C, ²H, etc.):
- Decay Analysis (¹³⁷Cs, ²¹⁰Pb, ³²Si):
- Archaeo-stratigraphy
- Bio-stratigraphy (index fossils, micro-fossils, pollen, etc.)
- Palaeontology
- Palaeosols
- Stratigraphy (Geology)
- Tephrochronology
- Chromatography
- DNA – Gene Sequencing
- Pigmentation (organic / inorganic) – Patination
- Painting Technique
- Seriation
- Desert Varnish (cation ratio)
- Surface Weathering Features
- Chemical Analyses (ICPMS, fluorine, ion beam, etc.):
- Material Characterisation (x-Ray, XRF, XRD, Raman, etc.):
- Microscopy (SEM, CT-Scan, etc.):
- Obsidian Hydration

11. General Field of Expertise.

When a Dating Service is requested in your institution, within which field does it fall? Check all that apply.

Check all that apply.

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Earth / Environmental Sciences / Natural Heritage
- Palaeontology
- Palaeo-anthropology
- Archaeology
- Physical Heritage (e.g. building materials, construction, architecture, etc.)
- Cultural Heritage (e.g., art, sculpture, painting, etc.)
- Other(s):

12. Number of Samples related to Heritage Sciences.

Based on the above, please provide an approximate percentage of samples dated / characterised in your institution per field, within any given year: which samples are from submitters (clients, collaborators, researchers, etc.) with a clear Archaeological – Physical – Cultural Heritage background vs. a more palaeo-environmental origin. *Please account for all that applies.*

Comment only when you choose an answer.

Please choose all that apply and provide a comment:

- Earth / Environmental Sciences / Natural Heritage: % Samples:
- Palaeontology: % Samples:
- Palaeo-anthropology: % Samples:
- Archaeology: % Samples:
- Physical Heritage:% Samples:
- Cultural Heritage:% Samples:
- Other(s):

13. Authentication – Certification – Verification.

Do you and/or your institution need authenticate / certify / verify archaeological- and/or Heritage-related materials?

Comment only when you choose an answer.

Please choose all that apply and provide a comment:

- Earth / Environmental Sciences / Natural Heritage: % Samples:
- Palaeontology: % Samples:
- Palaeo-anthropology: % Samples:
- Archaeology: % Samples:
- Physical Heritage:% Samples:
- Cultural Heritage:% Samples:
- Other(s)

14. Please specify your institution's needs in terms of type of material(s), site(s) and sample(s). *Please account for all that applies.*

Comment only when you choose an answer.

Please choose all that apply and provide a comment:

- Materials (e.g., rock; block; sediment; soil; minerals; ceramic; metal; paint; wood; charcoal; paper; teeth; textiles; pollen; bone, etc.):
- Most needs in:
- Least needs in:
- Sites (e.g., caves; marshes; high altitude; underground; castles; churches; painting; sculpture, etc.):
- Most needs in:
- Least needs in:
- Samples (i.e., loose vs. contained sample; types of containers; sediment cores vs. hand specimens, etc.):
- Most needs in:

- Least needs in:

15. Types of Services.

Please provide the Types of Services your institution request within any given year. Please detail % of samples accepted for each service and their priority within the institution's schedule. Please account for all that applies.

Comment only when you choose an answer.

Please choose all that apply and provide a comment:

- Commercial: % Samples: Priority:
- Routine Collaboration – Internal Research: % Samples: Priority:
- Experimental Collaboration – Internal Research: % Samples: Priority:
- National Laboratory QA Inter-comparisons / Standardizations: % Samples: Priority:
- International / EU Laboratory QA Inter-comparisons / Standardizations: % Samples: Priority:
- Calibrations / Verifications / Controls: % Samples: Priority:
- Maintenance / Mise à pointe: % Samples: Priority:
- Others: % Samples: Priority:

16. Self-Sufficient Institution.

Does your Institution (including Centre / Institution) have all the necessary facilities, equipment and personnel to perform a complete age determination and/or characterisation from A to Z? In other words, do you have a self-sufficient / self-contained institution with no need to reach out for third-party analyses to complete a dating procedure?

Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No
- If No, do you need to sub-contract other laboratories for specific intermediate analyses required for a complete age calculation / characterisation?

Make a comment on your choice here:

17. Equipment Capacity.

Describe the type of equipment you typically need for dating/characterization in your institution.

Comment only when you choose an answer.

Please choose all that apply and provide a comment:

- Name:
- Short Description:
- Dating Technique most used for:
- Dating Technique least used for:

18. Equipment Capacity.

In terms of equipment's use, how much of the following has your institution used and what is its estimated usage within a given year?

Choose one of the following answers.

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Specialised Dating Equipment: Quantity: % Usage in 1 year:
- Non-Specialised Dating Equipment:Quantity: % Usage in 1 year:
- Supplementary equipment needed to achieve an age calculation:Quantity: % Usage in 1 year:

Make a comment on your choice here:

19. Turn-around Times.

For any material/sample, sent by your institution, what is the average delivery time of the results? Please specify if the values given are in days, months or years.

Comment only when you choose an answer.

Please choose all that apply and provide a comment:

- Best Time:
Commercial Service Dating /Research Dating/ Experimental Dating:
- Average Time:
Commercial Service Dating/Research Dating/ Experimental Dating:
- Worst Time:
Commercial Service Dating/ Research Dating / Experimental Dating:

20. Sample Collection Rules – Access.

Depending on the dating technique and laboratory, samples may be collected by any individual (expert or non-expert) and sent directly to the laboratory or require the assistance of an expert for the recovery of any given sample. Do you think that the IPERION HS Paleoanthropology and Paleontology community should seriously consider these two opposing points of view and allow different types of access to different facilities/laboratories, depending on experience and dating method?

Choose one of the following answers.

Error in default value: is an invalid value for this question

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- YES, would you consider providing your access suggestions / regulations to IPERION HS Palaeoanthropology and Palaeontology community as an example? Yes/No:

- NO, do you consider that all accesses to IPERION HS Palaeoanthropology and Palaeontology community should be handled the same way? :Yes/No
- Other answer:

Make a comment on your choice here:

21. Sample Shipping Rules – Access.

If a sample (only related to the IPERION HS Palaeoanthropology and Palaeontology community Programme) is to be shipped by your institution, in terms of shipping and handling costs, who should be paying for them?

Choose one of the following answers.

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- They should be included as part of the IPERION HS Palaeoanthropology and Palaeontology community access package.
- The sender, whoever s/he might be, at their own cost.
- The recipient laboratory, at their own cost.

Make a comment on your choice here:

22. Laboratory & Data Location – Access.

For several types of Dating Techniques, it is imperative for the laboratory to be/operate in the vicinity of the research project, sample/material collection location. Is that a requisite for your Institution?

Choose one of the following answers.

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Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

Make a comment on your choice here:

23. IPERION HS Seal of Quality – Brand.

Would you encourage the development or be interested in the branding of IPERION HS as a sign/seal of quality, prestige and certification?

Choose one of the following answers.

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes

- If yes, would you be willing to participate in homogenisation, normalisation, standardization experiments and routines, as well as QC-QA inter-comparisons involving laboratories within the same dating domain, to improve and preserve IPERION HS quality?
- NO, please provide a short explanation:

Make a comment on your choice here:

24. Funding Capacity.

In general terms, please specify your Institution's general funding scheme, i.e., how does your institution run, considering the following types of funding and to which percentage.

Comment only when you choose an answer.

Please choose all that apply and provide a comment:

- Commercial service income: % Funds:
- Consultancy: % Funds:
- Research funds (national and/or international grants): % Funds:
- Industry contracts: % Funds:
- In-kind funds:% Funds:
- Private and/or philanthropic donations: % Funds:
- Regular Government input/income/contracts: % Funds:
- Core funding (internal): % Funds:
- Other(s): Please specify.: % Funds:

25. Institution Funding Potential.

Would your Institution be able or willing to self-fund experiments, collaborations and/or research?

Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No
- If yes, please specify. Please account for all that applies: 1 project every few years / 1 project per year / More than 1 project per year

Make a comment on your choice here:

26. Other comments or queries.

Please write your answer here:
